

PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS OF FORMATION OF COMMUNICATIVE READINESS OF MUSIC TEACHER FOR EDUCATIONAL ACTIVITIES

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Abstract: In this thesis, there are opinions about the pedagogical conditions for forming the communicative readiness of the future music teacher for educational activities.

Key words: Music education, communicative activity, pedagogical technology, scientific analysis.

Introduction:

The formation of a music teacher's communicative readiness for pedagogical activity is carried out on the basis of the teacher's orientation in organizing the educational process towards the approaches of general and musical pedagogy, towards the developed pedagogical conditions for the formation of a music teacher's communicative readiness for pedagogical activity.

Musical pedagogy is related to general pedagogy in matters of approaches to organizing the educational process. The research is based on a personal approach, which means the consistent design and implementation of a pedagogical process focused on the individual as a goal, subject, result and the main criterion of its effectiveness. Reflecting the main directions of the humanistic paradigm of education, the personal approach is aimed at students as subjects of life, at "freely developing integral individuals, focused on internal self-development, self-realization, interpersonal communication, dialogue, and assistance in personal and professional growth " In this work, this approach is the methodological basis for studying the issue of forming a music teacher's communicative readiness for pedagogical activity and presenting a music teacher as a person possessing the personal qualities necessary for pedagogical activity.

The activity approach states that activity is one of the factors in the formation of personality. Since pedagogical communication reflects interaction in the educational process, that is, pedagogical communication has an activity basis, the issue of forming a music teacher's communicative readiness for pedagogical activity can be considered in line with the activity approach.

The culturological approach involves the use in the educational process of the culture of the environment in which a particular educational institution is located, which, in turn, determines the content of education, the development of the student's personality, the preservation of its individuality and the satisfaction of needs. In this work, the culturological approach allows us to study the issue of forming the communicative readiness of a music teacher in a music-pedagogical environment, which, as a universal human culture, influences the manifestation of the student's individuality in communicative interaction, the manifestation of his ability in this interaction for cultural self-development and self-determination in the world of cultural values; allows us to identify students' attitudes towards the educational institution as a cultural and educational space in which information encoded in the content of education is transmitted.

Consideration in the work of the issue of communication in education and related issues of the content of general scientific and interdisciplinary concepts "interaction", "relationship", "communication", presented in the educational context, necessitated the use of an integrated approach in the work. An integrated approach allows for the integration of knowledge about qualities and state of personality of students and means of teaching; allows for the implementation of interdisciplinary connections in the pedagogical process, which contributes to the personal development of students - future music teachers and the formation of communicative readiness for teaching activities.

The technological approach involves the use in the educational process of technologies, techniques, schemes, algorithms that guarantee the achievement of the planned result. The use of the technological approach is due to the need to improve the structure and content of the music pedagogical training of music teachers, forms and methods of educational activities of the teacher, aimed at cooperation, interaction. The basis of the technological approach is a diagnostically set goal and sequential procedures (algorithms) for achieving it, which contributes to the development of students' skills in designing and constructing the educational process, ensuring the effectiveness of pedagogical interaction.

The technological approach allows us to consider the formation of a music teacher's communicative readiness for teaching activities in the process of information interaction between the teacher and students, to study the productivity of a combination of individual, group and collective forms of organizing the educational process.

Important components of the planned holistic educational process are the initial theoretical principles that determine its content, forms, methods and means, the nature of interaction, features of managing the cognitive and practical activities of students, taking into account the personal qualities of each, which ultimately ensures the achievement the desired result of pedagogical activity. The analysis of the scientific and theoretical approaches presented in the work, psychological and pedagogical research that develops issues of communication in education, made it possible to identify the principles of implementing pedagogical information and communicative interaction aimed at developing the communicative readiness of a music teacher for teaching activities:

1. The principle of conformity to nature. Based on the natural conditionality of information and communication interaction:

1) the presence of a physiological basis for communication - organs adapted for transmitting, receiving, interpreting, storing and reproducing information, which include the organs of hearing and memory;

2) the presence of a set of interhuman connections that unite participants in communication.

Successful communicative interaction, in which the teacher's activity is subordinated to the principle of conformity with nature, presupposes knowledge and consideration of the natural patterns of information exchange.

2. The principle of manufacturability. It manifests itself in the design, logical construction of communicative interaction, each stage of which is subordinated to the solution of a specific communicative task, and the entire communicative process carried out in a certain educational algorithm is aimed at achieving the planned result.

3. The principle of cultural conformity. It is based on the cultural conditioning of communicative interaction - the spontaneous and purposeful movement (transmission, exchange) of specific - "cultural" information in "certain cultural forms", which include art, religion, philosophy, mythology, etc. In the musical pedagogical process it is expressed in the presentation of musical works as cultural objects (objects of "cultural information") and their consideration in the system of information and communication interactions ("teacher - musical work - student", "composer - performer - listener" etc.) at the level of general culture, musical culture, social life, musical art.

The specifics of communicative interaction in the musical-pedagogical process are determined by the object of communication, which is not only a

verbal text, but also a musical text - a musical work that, like a verbal text, has pedagogical content and personally significant meaning. In the course of pedagogical communication, which is polysubjective in essence, a musical work is a source of information in a multifaceted communicative interaction - it is at the same time an object of interaction of various types and various levels (relative to social life, general and musical culture, musical art).

In confirmation, we repeat that communicative interaction, in which the object of communication is a musical work, is carried out in three types of information and communication interaction (in chains) operating in music education: "teacher - musical work - student", "composer - performer - listener", "social environment - culture - music". In each type of communicative interaction (in the chain), the interaction of educational communicative components manifests itself to one degree or another:

1) mutual influence of the environment of existence (verbal, non-verbal) and the sphere of development (*perception, memorization, understanding, reproduction*);

2) the interdependence of emotional and value ideas that have developed in society about music, and the personal priorities of future music teachers based on scientific and aesthetic ideas;

3) interaction between the educational sphere and the sphere of personal needs of the future music teacher for teaching activities.

The presented types of communicative interaction (*chain*) can also be considered in a broad communicative sense at the level of mutual influence of social e-life and musical art; interdependence of culture and music education; interaction between musical culture itself and education.

Conclusion:

The diversity of communication connections in which a musical work functions indicates the need to use highly artistic musical samples of different styles, trends and genres, and various areas of creativity in the educational process for educational purposes; to folklore, to spiritual, classical, modern music.

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